

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF IMPROVING THE SHOT PUT TECHNIQUE BASED ON KINEMATIC ANALYSIS

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Abstract. The article presents data reflecting the features of the shot put technique by athletes of the II category and I youth category. Quantitative values of individual kinematic parameters in the jump and final effort phases of mass athletes are given.

Keywords: shot put, final effort, jump, elite athletes, speed and acceleration of the shot.

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that achieving high sports results is possible under the condition of not isolated, but complex manifestation of various aspects of training: physical, technical, tactical, psychological, theoretical. Moreover, in the process of sports training, each of the parties is aimed at solving certain problems.

One of the most important tasks is to master the technique of the chosen sport, in particular the shot put technique, which meets certain requirements. Knowledge of the patterns, composition and structure of motor action allows you to control the process of formation of a motor skill, which, in turn, affects the assessment of the technique of a competitive exercise. Therefore, the study of the biomechanical features of a specific physical exercise is focused on finding a rational technique and improving their kinematic and dynamic structure [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Many specialists have been studying the shot put technique. Over the years, studies have been carried out on the analysis of competitive exercises in two ways: linear technique (linear swing) and rotational method (circular swing, "A. Baryshnikov's method"). The phases and features of their implementation in the structure of a holistic motor action are described [3]. In addition, the researchers presented the kinematic and dynamic characteristics of the shot put technique. The considered indicators, as a rule, were obtained by analyzing the technique of the strongest athletes [3].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ten shot putters took part in the study (five athletes of the II category and five athletes of the I youth category). Athletes performed shot put with a weight

of 5 kg (II category) and 4 kg (I youth category). The technique of the competitive exercise was analyzed.

The following methods were used in the work: high-speed video recording, biomechanical analysis.

When analyzing the shot put technique, the following elements are distinguished [4]:

- holding the core;
- preparatory phase for take-off (jump - linear swing, turn - circular swing);
- take-off jump (turn);
- final effort;
- phase of braking or maintaining balance [3].

Holding the core and the preparatory phase for the take-off create the conditions for the effective implementation of basic actions in subsequent phases.

The run-up is an important phase in the shot put. It begins with a swinging movement of the left leg, which, unbending at the hip and knee joints, is directed towards the segment. The phase ends with a two-support position.

The main phase in the shot put, on which performance depends, is the final effort. It is in this phase that the initial velocity of the projectile is communicated at the optimal angle.

As a result of solving the first problem, the following data were obtained. The entire pushing process from the jump to the release of the shot lasts about 1 second for category II athletes. In this case, the run-up jump takes about 0.7 s, and the final effort takes about 0.3 s. The length of the jump reaches 0.75–0.8 m. As studies have shown, the length of the application of force to the core in the final effort is 1.7 m.

For athletes of the first youth category, according to the measurement results, it can be noted that the total time of the jump and final effort is about 1.1 s (run-up jump - 0.75 s and final effort - 0.35 s). The length of the jump in this case reaches 0.65–0.7 m. As a result of the calculations, it turned out that the length of the application of force to the core in the final force is 1.6 m.

In the process of solving the second problem, the core velocity and acceleration in the jump and final force phases were found. During this period of time, there is an increase in the speed of the cannonball, which is a consequence of the run-up and the efforts of the thrower applied to the cannonball. At the same time, the nature of the speed change is somewhat different among athletes

of the presented categories. At the moment of projectile release, the speed of the cannonball for athletes of the II category was more than 10 m/s, and for athletes of the I youth category it was 9 m/s.

Analyzing the dynamics of core acceleration, it can be noted that athletes of these categories have several peaks. Thus, in category II athletes, until the corresponding moment of 0.493 s in the jump and final effort phases, acceleration increased. After this, the acceleration decreased. Its highest value was more than 300 m/s² and was observed at the moment of release of the core.

For athletes of the 1st youth category, the acceleration dynamics were somewhat different. The maximum acceleration was recorded at 0.544 s and was more than 250 m/s². After which the acceleration also decreased and at the end of the final effort phase increased again. Thus, at the moment of projectile release, the nature of the change in acceleration differed among athletes of both categories.

CONCLUSION

1. As a result of the study, quantitative indicators of the technique of the competitive exercise of shot putters were obtained. Thus, the duration of the jump and final effort phases is longer among athletes of the 1st youth category. The length of the jump and the application of force to the core in the final effort, on the contrary, is greater in category II athletes.

2. There are also differences in the dynamics of speed and acceleration. The highest value of the speed imparted to the core in athletes of both categories is observed at the end of the final effort phase. However, their values differ and are more than 10 m/s for athletes of the II category, and 9 m/s for athletes of the I youth category. The maximum acceleration for athletes of the 2nd category was noted at the moment of release of the shot, and for athletes of the 1st youth category in the jump phase.

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